

Benefits of Cochlear Implant in Children: The Parents Perspective

Asifa Zia

Demonstrator, Clinical Audiologist, FMH Institute of Allied Health Sciences Lahore, Pakistan

Faiza Mushtaq

Senior Demonstrator, Consultant Audiologist, FMH Institute of Allied Health Sciences Lahore, Pakistan

Fatima Rafique

Senior Demonstrator, Consultant Audiologist, FMH Institute of Allied Health Sciences Lahore, Pakistan

Atika Saleem

Consultant Audiologist, Hameed Latif Hospital Lahore, Pakistan

Accepted: 05 January 2024, Received in Revised form: 25 January 2024, Published: 07 February 2024

Abstract

Background and Objective: The language is the medium by which communicate and sound is the power source to understand the language these are our years and the hearing sense contact as with the word. The objective of this study is to analysis the subjective benefits of cochlear implantation in children according to parents' Perspective.

Method: It was carried out in children aged 2-3 years. A self-designed questionnaire was used to assess the potential point of view. The questionnaires were filled by parents included the following sections: hearing, communication and psychosocial. Decision to implant, process of implantation, positive effect of the implant, communication, supporting the child, self-reliance, well-being, happiness, social relationships, education, pre and postoperative services provided by the implant center. Parents of 50 children with congenital deafness or who became deaf between the age of 1 to 7 years and received cochlear implant were asked.

Results: The results of present study, cochlear implant had a positive effect on the quality of life of children and their families in different variety of ways. All things related to children had improvement in quality of life after cochlear implant activation. Parents were more satisfied with the domains self-reliance, communication and social relations because it affects more on child's life.

Conclusion: Access to auditory information helped the children to join the hearing world and to learn to speak. From the parent's perspective cochlear implant improves the quality of life of their children, especially when it comes to self-confidence, social relations and communication. Parents were more satisfied with their child's overall performance.

Keywords: Hearing impairment, Hearing loss, Cochlear implant, Communication, Psychosocial.

INTRODUCTION

Hearing loss is the most common disability in all over the world. According to WHO more than 1.5 billion people nearly 20% of the global population live with hearing loss.¹

Almost 3 to 4% children's have profound hearing loss. The cochlear implant has revolutionized the field of audiology. Just 50 years ago, there were no effective treatments for deafness and severe losses in hearing. The invention of CI changed that completely and now-a-days most individuals with CIs can communicate with ease using their cell phones. The advancement in CI technology has been both fast and effective.²

Alessandro Volta, who developed the electric battery, gave the first account of electrical stimulation of the auditory system. In the early 1800s, he connected each pole of a battery to a metal probe and inserted one probe into one of his ear canals and the other probe into the other canal. One of the probes had a switch to interrupt or allow the flow of current. He described his experience after closing the switch as a "jolt in the head," followed by a sound that resembled "a kind of crackling, jerking, or bubbling as if some dough or thick material was boiling". Broad widespread infant hearing screening has driven to expand distinguishing proof of newborn children having hearing loss around the world.³ There's presently copious prove that early implantation in children is profitable dialect. Children implanted between the ages of 12 and 36 months outflanked children implanted between the ages of 37 and 60 months. This, beside prior recognizable proof of childhood deafness, is pushing the age at implantation lower. For many a long time, the lower limit for age at implantation was 2. The primary clinical trial to assess a multichannel implant in children was the Nucleus 22 device. The primary clinical trial to incorporate children less than 2 years of age was with the Clarion gadget. The Clarion gadget may be demonstrated for children of 18 months. All cochlear implant gadgets can be securely shown for children of 12 months and more seasoned. As of 2000, the FDA has endorsed a gadget for implantation for those patients matured 12 months or more. In spite of the fact that earlier and continuous investigate has endeavored to address the interesting issues of security, candidacy, programming, and viability in this exceptionally youthful age. CI in children younger than 12 months of age remains controversial. Further reductions in age at implantation are currently limited by the nature of audiology testing in very young children. In general, using modern techniques, a confident assessment of severe to profound sensorineural hearing loss can be made in a child by the time they are 12 months old. In cases of hereditary hearing loss or meningitis, a confident assessment can sometimes be made at ages younger than this.⁴

The pediatric cochlear implant program was started in 1994 at St. Augustinus Hospital in 1994. The implantation was given to children younger than 2 years of age and in 2000 it was given to children younger than 1 year of age. For profoundly deaf children a steadily decreasing age and early clinical interventions were used for cochlear implantation.⁵ Although it is widely accepted that at the time of implantation, age is a significant factor for developing intelligibility and speech perception in pediatric implants. After cochlear implantation many pre-linguistically deaf children have experienced significant improvement in speech production, language skills and speech perception. Currently children are receiving cochlear implantations who are suffering from hearing impairment at a steadily decreasing age.⁶

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted at Audiology Department of Fatima Memorial College of Medicine & Dentistry (IAHS). The data was collected from the Audiology Center, Sir Syed Road, Gulberg-III,

Lahore. This study was completed within six months after the approval of synopsis. This study was observational descriptive study did not involve any treatment. About 50 cochlear implant subjects. Children with severe to profound degree of hearing loss using cochlear implant. A self-designed questionnaire used to collect the data according to the inclusive criteria.

Firstly, we counsel the parents of hearing-impaired children and a self-designed questionnaire used in data collection. And sure, about the questionnaire that it is valid and reliable in exploring parental views and experiences on outcomes of cochlear implants. The questionnaires comprise 20 statements with different aspects with communication, improvements, auditory skills, relation, education and self-confidence provided with multiple choices on five-point Likert scale: strongly agree, agree, do not know, disagree and strongly disagree. Data was collected from “Audiology Centre”, 63-3A, Liberty Homes, Block D-1, Opp. Hijaz Hospital, Sir Syed Road, Gulberg III, Lahore. No subject was put on experiment. So, no ethical issue in study.

It was a cross sectional study. Data was collected from Jinnah, General and UOL teaching hospitals. Study was completed within 6 months after the approval of synopsis. Sample size was 85. Patients were recruited conveniently through convenient sampling technique. Inclusion criteria for participation in the study involved having a medical diagnosis of hypertension by physician, being 20 years and older, and an attendance at the clinics of the any of the selected hospitals for a duration of at least 6 months before the study. Patents having Cancer, Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and Neurological conditions and Dementia was excluded.

Age and gender are a part of the personal identification number, and they are recorded practically without error. Their completeness and accuracy are shown by the fact that the matching of various registers according to the personal identification number was 100% complete.

DATA ANALYSIS

Data will be analyzed by using SPSS 23.0. (SPSS Inc. Chicago, USA). Appropriate statistical tools continuous variable like Age, Weight, was expressed as Mean, Standard Deviation whereas Categorical variable in form of frequency and percentage. Charts were used to display data and data will be analyzed by mean count standard deviation.

RESULTS:

1. Descriptive Analysis

The data was collected from parents of 50 hearing impaired children. A self-designed questionnaire was used for data collection and parents answered the questions after effective use of cochlear implant. The children were of age limit 1-6 years. Out of 50 subjects 34 are males and 16 females.

2. Gender of Patients

The gender distribution of hearing-impaired implant children is as, males were 34 out of 50 (68%) and the females are 16 out of 50 (32%).

Table 2. Gender of the patients

Gender	Frequency
Male	34(68%)
Female	16(32%)
Total	50(100%)

Graph 2. Gender of the patients

3. Age of Patients

Patients between age group of 2-4 years.

Table No.3. Descriptive Statistics of Age

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	50	2	4	4.62	1.4234

Graph 3. Statistics of Gender

4.1 Develop spoken language in children

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 7(14.0%) strongly agreed with this, 31(62.0%) agreed with this and 12(24.0%) gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	7	14.0
Agree	31	62.0
Neither agree nor disagree	12	24.0
Disagree	0	0
Strongly disagree	0	0

Table 4.1 develop spoken language in children

Graph 4.1 develop spoken language in children

4.2 Effective daily communication

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 5(10.0%) strongly agreed with this, 18(36.0%) agreed with this, 25(50.0%) gives neutral response and 2(4.0%) disagree with this were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	5	10.0
Agree	18	36.0
Neither agree nor disagree	25	50.0
Disagree	2	4.0
Strongly disagree	0	0

Table 4.2 effective daily communication

Graph 4.2 effective daily communication

4.3 Response on call

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 8(16.0%). Strongly agreed with this, 20(40.0%) agreed with this, 14(28.0%) Neither agree nor disagree, 6(12.0%) disagree with gives and 2(4.0%) strongly disagree response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	8	16.0
Agree	20	40.0
Neither agree nor disagree	14	28.0
Disagree	6	12.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0

Table 4.3 response on call

Graph4.3 response on call

4.4 Engage with others

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 11(22.0%) strongly agreed with this, 22(44.0%) agreed with this and 11(22.0%), 4(8%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	11	22.0
Agree	22	44.0
Neither agree nor disagree	11	22.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0

Table 4.4 engage with others

Graph 4.4 engage with others

4.5 Major Improvements

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 7(14.0%) strongly agreed with this, 21(42.0%) agreed with this and 18(36.0%), 4(8%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	7	14.0
Agree	21	42.0
Neither agree nor disagree	18	36.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	0	0

Table 4.5 major improvements

Graph 4.5 major improvements

4.6 Speech and language therapy improvements

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 9(18.0%) strongly agreed with this, 27(54.0%) agreed with this and 10(20.0%), 4(8%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	9	18.0
Agree	27	54.0
Neither agree nor disagree	10	20.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.6 speech and language therapy improvements

Graph 4.6 speech and language improvements

4.7 Way of response on sounds

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 4(8.0%) strongly agreed with this, 23(46.0%) agreed with this, 17(34.0%) neither agree nor disagree, 4(8.0%) Disagree with and 2(8.0%) strongly disagree gives were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	4	8.0
Agree	23	46.0
Neither agree nor disagree	17	34.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0

Table 4.7 way of response on sounds

Graph 4.7 way of response on sounds

4.8 Social isolation

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 10(20.0%) strongly agreed with this, 26(52.0%) agreed with this and 10(20.0%), 4(8.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	10	20.0
Agree	26	52.0
Neither agree nor disagree	10	20.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.8 social isolation

Graph 4.8 social isolation

4.9 Sociable with friends

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 5(10.0%) strongly agreed with this, 22(44.0%) agreed with this and 21(42.0%), 2(4.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	5	10.0
Agree	22	44.0
Neither agree nor disagree	21	42.0
Disagree	2	4.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.9 sociable with friends

Graph 4.9 sociable with friends

4.10 Relation with siblings

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 3(9.0%) strongly agreed with this, 21(42.0%) agreed with this and 20(40.0%), 6(12.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	3	6.0
Agree	21	42.0
Neither agree nor disagree	20	40.0
Disagree	6	12.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.10 relation with siblings

Graph 4.10 relation with siblings

4.11 Behavior improvement

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 4(8.0%) strongly agreed with this, 29(58.0%) agreed with this and 13(26.0%), 4(8.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	4	8.0
Agree	29	58.0
Neither agree nor disagree	13	26.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.11 behavior improvement

Graph 4.11 behavior improvement

4.12 Aware of things

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 4(8.0%) strongly agreed with this, 30(60.0%) agreed with this and 10(20.0%), 4(8.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	4	8.0
Agree	30	60.0
Neither agree nor disagree	10	20.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0

Table 4.12 aware of things

Graph 4.12 aware of things

4.13 Amuse with music and listening

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 7(14.0%) strongly agreed with this, 24(48.0%) agreed with this 11(22.0%) neither agree nor disagree and 6(12.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	7	14.0
Agree	24	48.0
Neither agree nor disagree	11	22.0
Disagree	6	12.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0

Table 4.13 amuse with music and listening

Graph 4.13 amuse with music and listening

4.14 Frustration after implant

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 11(22.0%) strongly agreed with this, 21(42.0%) agreed with this 16(32.0%) neither agree nor disagree with this and 2(4.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	11	22.0
Agree	21	42.0
Neither agree nor disagree	16	32.0
Disagree	2	4.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.14 frustration after implant

Grapes 4.14 frustration after implant

4.15 Daily activities after implant

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 6(12.0%) strongly agreed with this, 21(42.0%) agreed with this, 19(38.0%) neither agree nor disagree with this and 2(4.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	6	12.0
Agree	21	42.0
Neither agree nor disagree	19	38.0
Disagree	2	4.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0

Table 4.15 daily activities after implant

Graph 4.15 daily activities after implant

4.16 Education performance

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 6(12.0%) strongly agreed with this, 26(52.0%) agreed with this, 14(28.0%) neither agree nor disagree with this and 4(8.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	6	12.0
Agree	26	52.0
Neither agree nor disagree	14	28.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.16 education performance

Graph 4.16 education performance

4.17 Cope with mainstream school

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 7(14.0%) strongly agreed with this, 27(54.0%) agreed with this, 10(20.0%) neither agree nor disagree with this and 4(8.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	7	14.0
Agree	27	54.0
Neither agree nor disagree	10	20.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0

Table 4.17 cope with mainstream school

Graph4.17 cope with mainstream school

4.18 Child’s participation

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 5(10.0%) strongly agreed with this, 23(46.0%) agreed with this, 18(36.0%) neither agree nor disagree with this and 4(8.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	5	10.0
Agree	23	46.0
Neither agree nor disagree	18	36.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.18 child’s participation

Figure 4.18 child's participation

4.19 Child education with compare to normal students

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 6(12.0%) strongly agreed with this, 23(46.0%) agreed with this, 19(38.0%) neither agree nor disagree with this and 2(4.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	6	12.0
Agree	23	46.0
Neither agree nor disagree	19	38.0
Disagree	2	4.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.19 child education with compare to normal students

Graph4.19 child education with compare to normal students

4.20 Encourage your child

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 13(26.0%) strongly agreed with this, 23(46.0%) agreed with this, 10(20.0%) neither agree nor disagree with this and 4(8.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	13	26.0
Agree	23	46.0

Neither agree nor disagree	10	20.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.20 encourage your child

Graph 4.20 encourage your child

Discussion:

Communication is an important aspect of everyday life especially for children. Hearing loss can impair the exchange of information and therefore reduces the quality of life. The purpose this study is to assess the outcomes of cochlear implant at different ages. To find out these outcomes is necessary to have a focus vision about their mode of subject, this study analysis the subjective benefits of cochlear implantation in children according to their parents Perspectives. In 2013 a study was conducted by Sue M Archbold, et-al is to assess benefit of cochlear implantations according to their Perspective. They had parents of 70 children who become deaf between the ages of 1-6 year and receive cochlear implant. While in present study we identify the hearing-impaired children with severe degree hearing loss after using cochlear implant. Through a self-design questionnaire using COSI (Client orientation scale of improvement) scale. In present study we take sample from 50 implanted children and their families all over the age of 2-4 year of parents usually express great satisfaction with the quality of life in the children and the family after 2-3 years of cochlear implantation. The parents of child answer the question after the effective use of cochlear implant.

In 2012 a study was conducted by Govers-PJ and et-al, to analysis the young children outcome of cochlear implantation in relation to the age at implantation. In this study total 70 children participated. In present study we collected data from 50 subjects all over the age of 2-4 year after the 2-3 year of cochlear implantation. Applying a questionnaire to parents reflects the view of people deeply interested in the process and results after cochlear implant activation in children of different age groups. It is known that quality of life among children and adolescents who use cochlear implants similar to that of their normal hearing friends. Thus, the population of children using cochlear implant, the use of questionnaire with parents allows us to evaluate children’s quality of life, as well as their parents and relatives or the interaction between all of them.

Conclusion

In the present study, cochlear implantation, habilitation and speech therapy provided after the

surgery to improved quality of life of children and their families. Access to auditory information helped the children to join the hearing world and to learn to speak. From the parent's perspective cochlear implant improves the quality of life of their children, especially when it comes to self-confidence, social relations and communication. Parents were more satisfied with their child's overall performance.

REFERENCES

1. Suzuki JI, Kobayashi T, Koga K, editors. Hearing impairment: An invisible disability how you can live with a hearing impairment. Springer Science & Business Media; 2012 Dec 6.
2. Loizou PC. Introduction to cochlear implants. IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Magazine. 1999 Jan;18(1):32-42.
3. Thomas J, McDonagh D. Shared language: Towards more effective communication. The Australasian medical journal. 2013;6(1):46
4. Pensak ML, Choo DI, editors. Clinical otology. Thieme; 2014 Nov 15.
5. Pensak ML, Choo DI, editors. Clinical otology. Thieme; 2014 Nov 15
6. Lasak JM, Allen P, McVay T, Lewis D. Hearing loss: diagnosis and management. Primary Care: Clinics in Office Practice. 2014 Mar 1;41(1):19-31.